

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL-PRACTICAL ACTIVITY IN FUTURE TEACHERS BASED ON A REFLECTIVE APPROACH

Kholbotaeva Dilfuza

Doctoral student of RSIPS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10577738>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the processes of personal and professional development of future teachers, the importance of a reflexive approach in the step-by-step development of the professional activity of future teachers, the types of reflexive approach, the possibilities of using a reflexive approach in the development of professional and cultural worldviews of future teachers. Information on the formation of valuable motivational, cognitive and behavioral professional skills in future teachers with the help of a reflexive approach is also presented. This article can be a methodological resource for the general scientific community and future teachers.*

Keywords: *future teacher, reflexive approach, personal-professional development, professional-practical activity, professional competence, originality, self-development.*

The professional and cultural worldview of a future teacher is understood as the integrated content of a person's intellectual and valuable relationships. In this process, the future teacher appears as a subject of future pedagogical activity. The future teacher's professional and cultural outlook includes positive motivation for pedagogical activity, professional competence, self-awareness, originality, and the possession of important professional and personal qualities. These qualities develop effectively in the process of pedagogical practice. Among the effective methods of forming these qualities, it is necessary to include the development of the professional point of view of the future teacher. Reflection of pedagogical activity is important in this. It should be noted that the reflexive approach is widely used in the higher pedagogical education system of developed countries. In advanced models of training future teachers, a comprehensive system of professional development of teachers and mechanisms of regular self-improvement in professional terms apply. In this process, reflection is interpreted as a self-management mechanism of the pedagogue. Because reflection creates a convenient opportunity for the future teacher to regularly analyze the acquired professional knowledge and experience. Reflection creates a favorable situation for the future teacher to correct his behavior in the process of pedagogical communication. Reflection creates conditions for the future teacher to analyze his mental state and improve his work. Therefore, reflection serves as a basis for the development of the personality of a future teacher.

Reflection serves to consciously implement the educational activities of the future teacher. The unique aspect of reflection is that it can guide students intellectually in the process of training future teachers. In this, the forms of pedagogical activity related to the understanding of the essence of the professional knowledge to be mastered, mastering the methods of professional action, mastering the skills of planning the educational process and organizing one's own activities are mastered. That is why pedagogical reflection is a mechanism that ensures self-awareness as a subject of professional activity, understanding of its uniqueness, and the ability to imagine how it will be received by students. As a result, future teachers will be able to understand the purpose, structural structure, and means of activation of their activities with the help of reflection. This

indicates that the mechanisms of pedagogical reflection are formed in the process of professional training of future teachers. At the same time, the reflexive approach helps the future teachers to gradually develop their professional activity. Based on a reflexive approach, the development of the professional and cultural outlook of future teachers is carried out in two directions: a) professional; b) personal.

Professional development of future teachers requires improvement of professional qualifications. Professional development is often equated with professional training.

Personal development ensures that the pedagogue appears as an active subject of his professional activity. It shows that his cultural outlook is developed. It shows the development of valuable motivational and creative fields of future teachers. This encourages the teacher to develop himself.

Professional and cultural development of the teacher requires improvement of his social and professional activities with the help of reflection. The development of reflexive skills of future teachers creates a basis for transforming their activities into a system of subject-subject relations. Applying a reflexive approach to the process of developing a cultural worldview in future teachers gives students the opportunity to develop their personal experiences, to apply the knowledge necessary for critical thinking to cultural models. In the process of professional training of future teachers, in the development of their cultural worldview, along with providing them with professional and cultural knowledge of a theoretical nature, pedagogical practice based on reflexive foundations takes a special place. This is due to the changing dynamic character of the higher pedagogical education process. At the same time, the social demands placed on the pedagogue with modern professional knowledge require the implementation of a new approach to his professional and cultural development. For this, first of all, the future teachers themselves should have the ability and opportunity to implement pedagogical reflection. In this, they are required to rely on the current level of their personal practical activities and professional cultural worldviews, and to master the methods of pedagogical activity, approaching from the student's point of view, not from the teacher's point of view. In the process of pedagogical practice, future teachers are required to observe and reflect on the experiences of their mentors and teammates, methods of professional activity, and the current level of professional cultural worldviews.

Based on the use of a reflexive approach in the development of professional and cultural worldviews of future teachers, students are required to adapt to the teaching profession using the possibilities of pedagogical practice. As a result, the professional and cultural worldview necessary for the implementation of professional activities develops rapidly in them. In the process of pedagogical practice organized on the basis of a reflexive approach, future teachers are required to determine their actions based on certain parameters. Including

- to imagine oneself in the position of a teacher;
- thorough mastering of the subject content and teaching methodology;
- to have a clear idea of the students' knowledge level and capabilities according to their age;
- such as being able to systematically analyze their pedagogical results.

This provides an opportunity for future teachers to objectively assess their professional abilities and acquired professional knowledge. Future teachers should acquire the experience of carrying out their professional activities in accordance with the purpose and content of the curriculum. In doing so, they should be able to analyze their activities from the outside and

themselves, to present their developing, person-oriented, heuristic and competence approaches in the educational process in a mutually proportionate manner, to present the appropriateness of the used methods. It is of particular importance to be able to choose the methods and tools used in the implementation of the pedagogical process.

Applying a reflexive approach to any process requires observation. Such observation is carried out in the framework of the joint activity of experienced teachers and requirements in the process of pedagogical practice. In the process of observing the pedagogical activities of experienced teachers, students have the opportunity to analyze their work style, see the effective aspects of the methods and methods used by them, draw conclusions from a professional point of view, and develop their knowledge based on the results of their activities. They did. In addition, future teachers will be able to observe and analyze the results of each other's work methods and activities during pedagogical practice. In the process of practical educational activities, students should thoroughly prepare for pedagogical practice. On this basis, they apply and test the practical experience they have acquired. During pedagogical practice, future teachers participate in didactic situations of various nature. They imagine themselves in the position of a teacher. In this process, future teachers are required to thoroughly master the teaching methods of subjects included in the curriculum of general secondary educational institutions. Future teachers should be able to organize the learning process using the imitation method. Future teachers are required to discuss the work they have done together with their group mates, to provide information about the methods by which they solved the difficulties that arose. It is also assumed that they can give specific recommendations to eliminate the mistakes made by themselves and their teammates. In such situations, some students analyze the learning process from the student's point of view. This, in turn, makes it possible to accurately take into account the current level of students' capabilities, interests, and motivations when organizing different educational situations. It is assumed that future teachers will acquire the experience of taking into account the interests and needs of students, the ability to perform educational tasks of various complexity, and the methodological skills of the teacher. It can be seen that on the basis of reflexive approach, the foundations of practical pedagogical activity are formed in future teachers, as well as the pedagogical point of view characteristic of the future teacher is formed in them. Future teachers acquire values that are important for their personal professional development during pedagogical practice. In the process of practical training, they strive to master their professional experience, taking into account the gaps in their knowledge, skills and qualifications. Based on the results of pedagogical reflection, future teachers take the position of teachers and engage in interpersonal relationships with students. The complexity of the problem is that in the process of gaining professional experience, future teachers not only acquire knowledge, but also get accurate information about their psychological characteristics. Based on the acquired knowledge, future teachers conduct training with students in the process of pedagogical practice, choose topics based on their psychological characteristics and organize class hours. Reflexive activity is extremely necessary for future teachers, because the pedagogical activity carried out as a test and the experiences used are not free from errors and shortcomings. That is why the reflexive approach during pedagogical practice is important in forming the professional point of view of future teachers. That is why future teachers have professional competencies based on the approach of cultural studies. It is important to use a reflexive approach in the formation of. With the help of a reflexive approach, valuable motivational, cognitive and behavioral professional skills are formed in future studies. At the same

time, the reflexive approach helps future teachers to understand pedagogical skills at the level of professional value. As a result, future teachers will have the opportunity to improve their pedagogical activities in the future. In this way, a professional point of view and a professional cultural outlook are formed in them.

REFERENCES

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018-yil 28-noyabrdagi “O‘zbekiston Respublikasida milliy madaniyatni yanada rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida”gi PQ-4038-son Qarori.
2. Obuxov, A.S. Refleksiya v proektnoy i issledovatel'skoy deyatelnosti [Tekst] / A.S. Obuxov // Issledovatel'skaya rabota shkolnikov. — 2005. - № 3. - S. 19-38.
3. Safarova R.G. Computer-didactic support for the training of social sphere specialists at the university based on a cultural approach. International conference: Problems in the Textile and Light Industry in the Context of Integration of Science and Industry and Ways to Solve Them (PTLICISIWS-2022). 050009 Scopus, Web of Science indexed. <http://pubs.aip.org/aip/acp>
4. Safarova R.G. Mechanisms of applying the cultural science approach to the didactic process based on the integration of pedagogical subjects. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 9 SEPTEMBER 2023 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337. P 495-499